

FOREST4EU partner: Cesefor

OG: Suber

OG's country:

Type of Innovation: to be filled...

New cork uses guide

Introduction

Gosuber project, developed from 2018 to 2020, has been oriented to improve cork harvesting efficiency. An attempt has been made to establish a cork quality classification procedure.

Main results have been materialized in a guide, that collect detailed information about the studies carried out and their applications in cork quality classification.

Information technologies applied to subericulture are the immediate future of forest management of cork oak forests.

The possibility of establishing the different qualities of cork in the field through innovative technologies will lead to a democratization of cork sales standards.

The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

<https://gosuber.es/>

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